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Fund of the Presidents of Ukraine, V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine),
e-mail: strungar@nbuv.gov.ua, ORCID 0000-0002-6706-8427**Legal Resources of Historical and Cultural Heritage: Presentation in Library Collections and Their Popularization**

Objective: to substantiate the significance of historical documents of legal concern in digital library resources of historical and cultural heritage as an important component of cultural memory; to generalize modern approaches to improving the popularization of these library resources in the information space. **The methods** of systematic analysis of library databases of historical and cultural heritage have been used in the research, in particular, the V. I. Vernadsky National Library (Ukraine), World Digital Library, Europeana, Gallica, Bavarian State Library, etc. **Results.** The monuments of law as a component of historical and cultural heritage, which need to be popularized in the information space, given the scientific, educational, and ideological significance, have been studied. **Conclusions.** The resources of monuments of law testify to the longevity of historical development, the heredity of legal culture, and the involvement of Ukrainian political and legal thought in the European context. Digitization of such documents and their inclusion in digital collections expands user access to monuments of law and intensifies their circulation in the cultural information space. Effective work directions on the popularization of digital sources of historical and cultural heritage according to the results of the analysis of foreign experience are the use of mobile technologies and the representation of resources in social media.

Keywords: historical and cultural heritage; monuments of law; digital libraries; mobile technology, social media

Introduction

An important task facing Ukrainian society at the present stage is the formation and strengthening of the worldview values-based orientations of citizens that determine their patriotic focus, and thus – it will determine political and civic behaviour. To solve this issue, we need the formation of a full-fledged national information space, overcoming its existing destruction, filling it with information that will contribute to the formation of a common, constructive vision of the national future. Building such a common vision involves, among other things, an appeal to the past and, importantly, to successful projects in it, examples of harmony between the individual and the state.

In this context, among the many areas of national cultural heritage, the monuments of law deserve special attention. They are fundamental for illustrating the state's progress from historical times to the present ones and affirm the longevity of the political and legal tradition. Monuments of law by their nature comprehensively reveal various aspects of public life in a certain historical period – economic and social relations, and political system. What is more, based on ideas relevant

to their time, they characterize the level of intellectual understanding of social development and are even the subject of linguistic discussions, as they provide material for clarifying the features of language practices of their time. Their complex, integrative nature determines the significance of the monuments of law at the present stage of understanding the national past: they have not only scientific, but also ideological value, and they are promising in terms of the educational process. The monuments of law are logically a part of the national myth – such as the Magna Carta, the Declaration of Independence of the United States, the Constitution of Pylyp Orlyk, the Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen, 26 August 1789, etc.

An important way to promote the national cultural heritage in recent decades has been a variety of national and international digital projects aimed at "informing and inspiring", preserving and expanding access to critical cultural treasures and important historical documents "for fun, education and research"; filling the information space with various cultural content.

Analysis of studies and publications. Ukrainian scientists are actively developing issues of both the general role of memory institutions in shaping the sociocultural environment (Dubrovina, Kyrydon, & Matiash, 2017; Dubrovina, Lobuzina, Onyshchenko, & Boriak, 2020; Rybachok, 2017) and the functioning and development of individual projects of integrated digital resources (Dobrovolska, 2020; Lobuzina, Perenesienko, & Loshhinskaja, 2019). Technological aspects of creating and ensuring the functioning of such projects, taking into account modern requirements for digital library resources and sources of scientific information, have also been reflected in historiography (Lobuzin & Perenesienko, 2020). Thus, the scientific challenge of digital representation of the national cultural heritage is being developed quite actively. However, given the dynamic development of digital resources, the constant emergence of new technologies and areas of work, scientific interest in the issue is preserved. At the same time, we can talk about the evolution of this interest – along with research on the formation of digital resources, the issue of support and management of digital information collections, their promotion is being brought up to date. Active assimilation of national cultural heritage by society, which due to libraries, archives, and museums became available through digital resources, their introduction into educational, popular science, artistic discourses is an important task both at the practical level of organization of activities of cultural and scientific institutions and at the level of scientific understanding.

Thus, the **objective of the study** is to generalize modern approaches to improving the promotion of library resources, in particular, the documents of legal concern of digital library collections of historical and cultural heritage as an important component of cultural memory in the information space.

Methods

The methods of systematic analysis of library databases of historical and cultural heritage have been used in the research. In particular, the V. I. Vernadsky National Library (Ukraine), World Digital Library, Europeana, Gallica, Bavarian State Library, etc. The use of social and cultural methods allows for finding out the features of the audience of the educational process, the specifics of perception, and the assimilation of information by modern youth. The study of the specifics of mobile application use in social and cultural processes requires a combination of methods of technical sciences and humanities. The integration of the methods of humanities and information technology has provided research on technologies for accessing and popularizing resources and collections.

Results and Discussion

The active popularization of the monuments of political and legal public opinion for Ukrainian realities acquires special significance for several reasons. Firstly, given the long stateless existence of Ukrainians, it is the evolution of legal thought, expressed by specific monuments (from medieval "truths" through the documents of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, Rus and Samogitia when the Ukrainian (Rus) nobility defended not only their class privileges but also national status, to the monuments of the Cossack state and further – documents of the period of the First Liberation Struggles), which is among the elements of assimilation and mastering of the past. Emphasizing the continuity and succession of norms and institutions of law, along with emphasizing the organic combination of local and European sources, is an important element in establishing the longevity of the Ukrainian political and legal tradition in the public consciousness.

Equally important is the emphasis on the corpus of Ukrainian monuments of law and in terms of stay of Ukrainian lands within foreign countries, therefore, the commonality of these monuments with the history of Lithuania, Poland, Belarus, Austria, and Russia, their representation in the national collections of these states, sometimes – as exclusively their monuments. Thus, there is a need to emphasize their Ukrainian nature (or Ukrainian component), and the active introduction of documents and information about them into the national information space. An important factor in this emphasis, its visualization, and expression is the representation by the institutions of memory of book monuments as historical, cultural, and legal sources.

Therefore, the activity of libraries on the accumulation, preservation, representation, and popularization of such documents of national memory is becoming especially important. V. I. Vernadsky National Library is not only the largest holder in Ukraine of an invaluable collection of unique and rare documents on the history of national law but also a scientific institution that systematically and actively carries out works on their presentation in the digital information space.

The main projects on the accumulation, presentation and dissemination of cultural heritage are the resources of the VNLU – Digital Library of Historical and Cultural Heritage, which contains a number of valuable and unique legal documents and a consolidated bibliographic and electronic resource of the documentary heritage of Ukraine – "Ukrainika Electronic Library", which is an analogue of digital projects of national libraries of other countries (Polona, Gallica, American memory, Canadiana, etc.). The collections of sources of law in these resources occupy a prominent place – the monuments of law in the Digital Library of Historical and Cultural Heritage are cross-presented in the categories "History" and "Jurisprudence"; an electronic library "Ukrainika" accumulates relevant resources under the categories "History", "State and Law".

Among the monuments of law that are of interest as sources for research, awareness-raising, educational projects, both due to historical and socio-political value, and accessibility for widespread use through the technology of digital libraries and collections, one should note the Statutes of the Grand Duchy of Lithuanian Rus', Samogitian as worded in 1529, 1566 and 1588 presented in digital collections of the VNLU; documents disclosing the contractual relations of the Zaporozhian Army with the Moscow tsars; a facsimile of the Ukrainian-language original of the Covenants and the Constitution of Rights and Freedoms of the Zaporozhian Army; a collection of norms of the Hetmanate of the XVIII century "Rights under which the Little Russian people are judged"; documents relating to the legislation of the Austro-Hungarian and Russian empires; documents disclosing the law-making and law-enforcement of the period of the First Liberation Struggle and the Soviet era.

The materials presented in the collections of the "Archive of South-Western Russia" series are noteworthy. They include acts on Ukrainian administrative, marriage, and family law,

materials on the history of local government, and public relations of the XV-XVII centuries. In a user-friendly form, there are such important and interesting documents for research and introduction not only in scientific but also educational and popular science discourse, as privileges and charters of princes of the GDL (Grand Duchy of Lithuania) and Polish kings to the Ukrainian nobility, to cities – on Magdeburg law and others aspects of governance, confirmation of the "rights and privileges" of the burghers by kings and voivodes; charters on peasant and bourgeois duties, a number of "supplications" – both noble and commonwealth appeals, court verdicts and decrees; protocols of self-governing bodies; also "Sejm constitutions" (decisions) on cities; documents determining the legal status of fraternities; documents on the functioning of sejmiks and delegation to higher bodies; evidence of property conflicts, recognition of status and responsibilities, etc.

It should be noted here that the trend according to which in the collections of historical and cultural heritage a prominent place is occupied by monuments that reveal the formation of the state, the struggle for human rights, and therefore belong to the realm of law, is a characteristic feature of digital projects. For example, the World Digital Library on keyword queries (in English): "law" provides 292 links to old prints that can be viewed by the user; "declaration" – 1015 links, "constitutions" – 982, "proclamation" – 335; "legislation" – 321. Europeana on similar inquiries gives the following result: "law" – 2300 sources, "constitutions" – 205, "declaration/proclamation" – 1377, "legislation" – 1377. Among these documents – there are the most various monuments – from handwritten "barbaric truths" of medieval Europe to the first editions of constitutions and declarations of the New Age.

As already mentioned, the presentation in digital collections of a wide range of documents that reveal the features of lawmaking and law enforcement in historical retrospect is an important area of formation of the national information space. At the same time, an important task is to ensure the usability of these documents, and their circulation in the information space, creating conditions for constant access to them by users.

Along with traditional methods, there are virtual and real exhibitions, events dedicated to memorable dates associated with some documents, the latest information and communication technologies deserve attention and widespread use. We will dwell on the use of mobile technology for access to library resources and features of representation of library projects and funds in social media.

Current trends in media consumption, characterized by the growing role of mobile devices and the intensification of their use in the consumption of scientific and cultural information produced by various information centers, including libraries, bring up to date the trend of adapting servicing with information resources to them (Bondarenko, 2016). Intensification of "mobilization" of libraries, which provides speed, convenience, personalization, and interactivity of user servicing, takes place in two directions – expanding the number of users willing to consume library mobile content and complicating the range of library services provided by mobile technology. If the adaptation of library websites to mobile versions is the initial stage of the mentioned "mobilization", the disclosure of unique funds or publications stored in special collections of the library requires additional requirements for mobile applications¹.

The creation of thematic mobile applications allows you to single out and disclose documents of special historical, cultural and artistic value from special library collections. A number of national and state libraries thus distribute resources of national and historical

¹ Mobile applications are computer programs created specifically for use on a mobile device, designed to perform some tasks as one of the tools of up-to-date communication, in particular, dissemination and promotion of scientific and socio-cultural information resources.

significance. An important thing in the presentation of digital collections, according to the analysis of LOC Collections applications of the Library of Congress, Gallica online library, Bavarian State Library, World Digital Library, Europeana is not only the accessibility and search through mobile devices to millions of documents of digitized collections, but also, given the features of the screens – the technology of presenting documents in full, with a scaling-up option of certain details.

Equally important is the increase in interactivity in working with documents – the ability to add to the list of favorites by creating your own selections of collection objects and sharing them with other users, downloading, e-mailing documents, or distributing via social media, creating tools for further promotion of such resources. Current mobile technology recently used by libraries in the context of promotion of their resources and making access to them easier is augmented reality features, such as 3D image recognition, where digital objects are displayed on the screen of a mobile device in a real place (for example, related to a document) and time. Such technologies are allocated to a separate group of AR applications. In this context, the British project SCARLET (Special Collections using Augmented Reality to Enhance Learning and Teaching) is noteworthy. It was introduced to improve the use of special collection materials in teaching and learning to help students interact with primary sources and facilitate their access to Internet resources. As part of the SCARLET project, the University of Manchester and Jisc, an advanced technology and services research company, have developed an AR application for collections of outstanding rare books, manuscripts and archives stored in the John Ryland Library. The project aims to remove one of the main obstacles to the use of special collections in teaching and learning – the need to work with archives, manuscripts and rare books in controlled reading rooms, isolated from most other supporting materials and the growing mass of related digital resources. The augmented reality project allows a large number of students at any time to explore in detail the delicate and valuable academic materials that would otherwise be locked behind display windows or would not be available to everyone. The rich variety of materials that can be linked virtually to objects allows students to immerse themselves in the subject and its relevance in ways that were previously unthinkable. This methodology has been designed with the expectation that it can be used by other libraries holding special collections, making them available for research, teaching and learning.

Another important area of promotion and popularization of library content of historical and cultural heritage is the intensification of interaction between libraries and social media. Due to the fact that legal documents that are the subject of our scientific interest are represented mainly by visual content or full-text versions in PDF format, the most promising social media in terms of representation of these documents are graphic and video content networks, such as Flickr, Instagram, Pinterest. Despite the existing functional differences, they can all be considered as photo hosting networks, in which libraries present their activities through a stream of collections grouped by thematic or another principle of visual content (albums) with accompanying information and systematization through tagging, with the possibility of user discussion, evaluation, download, and publication of library materials in other networks and adding user content. In addition, networks are a way to promote the library's official website by providing links to detailed information and embedding recommendation tools that allow viewing of similar thematic collections. The results of the analysis of library galleries on these social networks showed that the leader of these networks in terms of the number of readers and downloaded works is the Library of Congress of the United States. Active users of social media for the promotion of historical and cultural monuments are also the British Library, Harvard Library, etc. Expectedly, the most popular documents of the Library of Congress are monuments outlining the formation of the state – Declaration of Independence, Constitution of the United States, Bill of Rights; a significant place is occupied by collections relating to the movement for rights of various groups:

abolitionist, suffragette, etc. The legal "gem" in the British Library's collections is the Magna Carta and related documents and artifacts. It is revealing that even presenting the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen of 1789, the British Library emphasizes its imitation of the Grand Charter of Liberties "in some basic principles".

It is noteworthy that in the case of the popularization of library collections and funds on social media, it is a combination of different forms of representation – social networks publish digitized memorabilia and inform about the presentation of these documents in traditional library exhibitions. The presentation of the monuments includes significant scientific and educational work, the creation of a large-scale reference block, which is also represented on social networks.

Conclusions

The importance of popularizing the monuments of law in the funds and collections of libraries is determined by their ideological influence, scientific, educational, awareness-raising potential. Filling the national information space with relevant information is a component of image strategies for cultural and historical positioning in the global space, and an important component of establishing a national vision of the past, the longevity of historical development, heredity of legal culture, and involvement in the global context. The digitization of such documents and their inclusion in digital collections characterizes the activities of the world's leading libraries, thus expanding user access to monuments of law, and intensifying their circulation in the cultural information space. Additional tools for promoting digital sources of historical and cultural heritage based on the results of the analysis of foreign experience are the use of mobile technology and the representation of resources in visual content social media. These measures make it possible to expand the circle of users, improve the disclosure of library funds, simplify access to resources, and increase their circulation in society. At the present stage, the popularity of thematic library applications created to promote national cultural heritage is growing; the popularization of historical and cultural, in particular, legal resources through social media tools remains relevant.

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Правові ресурси історико-культурної спадщини: представлення в бібліотечних колекціях та їх популяризація

Мета дослідження. Обґрунтувати світоглядне, освітнє, культурне значення історичних документів правового спрямування у цифрових бібліотечних ресурсах історико-культурної спадщини як важливої складової культурної пам'яті. **Методологія.** У дослідженні використано методи системного аналізу бібліотечних баз даних історико-культурної спадщини. **Результати.** Досліджено пам'ятки права як складової історико-культурної спадщини, що потребує популяризації в інформаційному просторі з огляду на наукове, освітнє, світоглядне значення. **Висновки.** Ресурси пам'яток права засвідчують тяглість історичного розвитку, спадковість правової культури, включеність української політико-правової думки в європейський контекст. Оцифрування таких документів та включення їх до цифрових колекцій розширює користувацький доступ до пам'яток права, інтенсифікує їх циркуляцію у культурному інформаційному просторі. Ефективними напрямками роботи з популяризації цифрових джерел історико-культурної спадщини за результатами аналізу зарубіжного досвіду є застосування мобільних технологій та репрезентація ресурсів у соціальних медіа.

Ключові слова: історико-культурна спадщина; пам'ятки права; цифрові бібліотеки; мобільні технології; соціальні медіа

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